

ISic3663

I.Sicily inscription 3663

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

tufa (conchigliifero)

Object

aedicula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 37252

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR108278

1. M (arcus) Cano (leius)

2. Eros

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

EDR 108278

Bibliography

Gabrics, E. 1929. Stele sepolcrali di Lilibeo a forma di Heroon. *Monumenti Antichi*. 33: 41-60. At 57-58

Vento, M. 2000. Le stele dipinte di Lilibeo. Marsala. At 106-108 tav.77

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